

Research Methods and Tools – Report 1

Deliverable 2.3

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.3 Research Methods and Tools – Report 1
Version 1

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Executive summary

The purpose of this report is to document the objectives, content and implementation process of the Research Methods and Tools 1 (RMT1) course. The course is worth 4 ECTS, which is equivalent to about 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work. As indicated in the RE-DWELL research proposal, RMT1 introduced the main concepts of the RE-DWELL research structure: sustainability, affordability, and transdisciplinarity. Moreover, the course aimed to stimulate ESRs to critically engage with these concepts by integrating them in their research projects.

Participants evaluated the course through an online survey, the results of which are presented in Annex 1. The content of the course generally scored highly (4 out of 5 points), while the learning objectives scored satisfactorily (3 to 4 out of 5 points). The written feedback highlights that the course fulfilled the requirements of the kick-off phase of the project: ESRs were introduced to the key terms of RE-DWELL's research and were able to link them to their research projects. In addition, they were able to develop their academic writing and peer reviewing skills.

Important takeaways for the design of future RMT courses include a clearer management of expectations, for example, to provide 80% self-work per ECTS, which gives ESRs an important responsibility to link the learning activities as smartly as possible to the progress of their dissertation. Furthermore, the link between learning activities and learning objectives could be strengthened. Also, ESRs expressed a preference for more interactive sessions and shorter lectures, as well as more guidance on techniques for preparing fieldwork and understanding the academic literature. ESRs will also be asked for feedback on the course design before the next course starts.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to document the work carried out in the Research Methods and Tools 1 (RMT1) course: aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, and outputs. RMT1 introduced the main concepts of the RE-DWELL research framework (sustainability, affordability, transdisciplinarity). Moreover, RMT1 aimed to encourage the ESRs to critically engage with these concepts, integrating them into their research projects where appropriate, cumulating in the presentation of their first literature review in an essay and in the review of each other's work.

Université Grenoble Alpes (UGA), TU Delft, La Salle-URL and University of Reading (UREAD) prepared and provided the RMT1 content. In the final session, most RE-DWELL beneficiaries contributed (see Section 5).

Due to the pervading Covid-19 restrictions, the course took place mostly online, with two hybrid sessions during the Lisbon Workshop and the Nicosia Summer School. RMT1 was organized in seven sessions, which included synchronous sessions and self-directed work.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2, course aims; Section 3, learning outcomes; Section 4, course structure; Section 5, learning activities; Section 6, resources; Section 7, outputs and Section 8 evaluation. The feedback of participants is important as their answers revealed their preferred type of learning activities, and this information will be used in the development of future courses namely RMT2 and RMT3.

2. Course aims

RMT1 is one of three research and methods modules, which together aim to foster an appropriate theoretical grounding of the ESRs' research projects in a transdisciplinary manner. RMT1 was specifically designed for RE-DWELL purposes by UGA (lead organization: Adriana Diaconu), TU Delft (Marietta Haffner) and UREAD (Flora Samuel) with the aim to assist ESRs with the start of their research projects.

More specifically, RMT1 has the following learning aims:

1. To initiate collaboration between ESRs in order to start supporting the creation of a research network across their projects.
2. To support the development of the ESRs' individual research projects by consolidating their disciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge and methodological standpoints.

3. Learning outcomes

On the successful completion of the RMT1 module, the ESRs were expected to demonstrate the following outcomes:

- Understanding of different approaches to transdisciplinarity.
- Understanding of different disciplinary perspectives to housing research.
- Ability to analyse and position their own research and that of another ESR within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines.
- Ability to analyse different research approaches to housing issues in terms of methods and methodological mix (interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, etc.).
- Ability to analyse the use of two fundamental concepts of housing studies - housing affordability and housing sustainability - and apply them in their own research work.

- Ability to create a transdisciplinary research proposal in which they defend their own approach to transdisciplinarity based on the critical synthesis of the course materials.

4. Course structure

Figure 1 shows the timeline for the RMT1 course, the links with the start-up week in July of 2021, and other network activities (contribution to the online RE-DWELL vocabulary), as well as the sessions of TS1 course which ran in parallel to RMT1.

Figure 1. RMT1 course structure as integrated with the network activities

Table 1 provides an overview of the programme structure with dates (July-November 2021) and time slots, session titles, brief content descriptions as well as the lead RE-DWELL staff. Further information is provided in Section 5 Learning activities.

Table 1. RMT1 session briefs

Date (CET)	Sessions	Lead
16.7.21 14:00-14:30 online	Presentation of the course and of the different ESR individual and collective tasks and expected submissions.	Adriana Diaconu (Université Grenoble Alpes)
16.7.21 14:30-16:00 online	Session 1: Introduction to transdisciplinarity The session will introduce the complex discussion on transdisciplinarity. Through an introduction of basic principles of multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary, ESRs will further critically analyse the existing literature and answer questions about their own research project in order to build their research framework in a transdisciplinary way.	Marja Elsinga (Delft University of Technology)
3.9.21 14:00-17:00 online	Session 2: Housing affordability and affordable housing provision The session explores conceptual as well as empirical information. The first part of the session explores the concept of housing affordability from the consumer point of view: what factors affect it and how can it be measured to identify 'sustainable' access to living in housing. In the second part of the session, examples of the provision of affordable housing and trends therein from different European countries are presented and discussed.	Marietta Haffner and Gerard van Bortel (both Delft University of Technology)
17.9.21 14:00-16:00 online	Session 3a: Housing sustainability Introduction to the origin of the terms sustainability, sustainable developments, and their changing meanings over time. Sustainable and affordable housing represented in the Sustainable Development Goals (goals, indicators and targets).	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
23.9.21 8:00-11:30 Workshop 1	Session 4: Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing Public roundtable with invited researchers (outside RE-DWELL) on inter-, cross- or trans-disciplinary research on housing, including a reflection on the history of housing research. This session will showcase examples of different approaches to housing issues aiming to transcend disciplines and/or to link research and practice. ESRs will be encouraged to reflect on their own position within the debate.	Adriana Diaconu (Université Grenoble Alpes) and Flora Samuel (University of Reading)
8.10.21 14:00-16:00 online	Session 3b: Housing sustainability Interlinking affordable and sustainable housing: what does sustainable housing mean? Sustainable design and building: a universal, overarching paradigm for contemporary architecture.	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
15.10.21 14:00-17:00 online	Session 5: Vocabulary workshop Group presentations and workshop on key terms definitions and theoretical frameworks.	Flora Samuel (University of Reading) and Jean-Christophe Dissart

	Based on the group work initiated in the beginning of the course (SESSION 1) the ESRs will identify and define (with reference to the literature) key terms that they will be using in their projects. The ESRs will submit three relevant terms in advance of the session and will be clustered into groups of two or three to work on defining one of these terms during the session. The definitions will be presented to the group for review and discussion. The definitions will be refined and presented as a RE-DWELL vocabulary entry to be submitted after the workshop (Task 1).	(Université Grenoble Alpes)
17.11.21 11:00-13:45 15:15-17:30 Summer School 1	<p>Session 6: Mapping the (trans)disciplinarity of the ESR's research</p> <p>In the sessions of the Nicosia Summer School dedicated to RMT1 the ESRs will have submitted their essays written as part of the RMT1 course (Task 2) and will peer-review the essay of another designated ESR (Task 3).</p> <p>Based on these presentations, a collective mapping of the disciplinary approaches put forward by the different research projects will be elaborated. This second map will reflect the structure acquired by the network, first five months after the initial mapping exercise realized during the Introductory days.</p>	Adriana Diaconu (Université Grenoble Alpes)

RMT1 was designed to offer a combination of asynchronous and synchronous (online and in-person) learning opportunities. This included online lectures, online workshops (group exercises, discussions and peer reviews), as well as some hybrid forms of activities. RMT1 implemented three learning events:

- Online seminars: online lectures followed by group work and/or discussion.
- Hybrid (in-person and online) public roundtable at Workshop 1 (Lisbon).
- Hybrid workshop at Summer School 1 (Nicosia), where the ESR essays were discussed.

In total RMT1 provided 4 ECTS to the RE-DWELL education programme (Table 2). The distribution across activities did not completely coincide with 25 hours per ECTS as Table 2 shows. The RMT1 continuous course activities 60 hours of learning (rather than 50), while this overshooting was compensated with the contribution to Workshop 1 (Lisbon) that amounted in total to 17.5 hours (rather than 25 hours).

Table 2. RMT1 learning type by type of activity, event and ECTS (1 ECTS = 25 hours)

Events	Course	Workshop 1	Summer School 1
	50 hours (2 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)
Online seminars	12	x	x
F2F lectures	x	x	x
F2F workshops	x	x	x
Hybrid workshop	x	x	5
Hybrid public roundtable	x	3.5	x
Presentations	x	x	x
Tutorials	x	x	x
Independent learning (80%)	48	14	20
Actual total hours	60	17.5	25

5. Learning activities

RMT1 offered learning opportunities during July, September and October, and the public roundtable with external speakers during Workshop (WS1) in Lisbon (September), and a seminar at the Summer School in Nicosia (November). The sessions summarized in Table 1 are described in detail in the following sections.

5.1. Session 1: Introduction to transdisciplinarity (16.7.21)

The online seminar entitled “Transdisciplinarity: definitions and principles” will deal with different definitions of transdisciplinarity and will evaluate the implications for RE-DWELL. The principles of transdisciplinarity will be explained and possible applications to affordable and sustainable housing will be discussed in groups. This session will make a start for a transdisciplinary framework for RE-DWELL and produce input for the public roundtable at Workshop 1.

Learning aims:

- To introduce ESRs to the different definitions of transdisciplinarity.
- To discuss the principles of transdisciplinarity and explore how these can be applied to affordable and sustainable housing.

Learning outcomes:

- Identify and explain different definitions and principles of transdisciplinarity.
- Critically reflect on what transdisciplinarity could mean for the PhD-work and the RE-DWELL project.
- Start exploring methods, cooperation and other means to make transdisciplinary work.

The seminar will take place from 14:30-16:00 CET. A lecture will be followed by a discussion in groups.

Group learning activities:

- To explore the development of a framework for the RE-DWELL project and the individual ESRs.
- To develop a transdisciplinary approach of affordable and sustainable housing.

Group discussion:

- What is the shared problem in affordable and sustainable housing?
- What is your ESR-contribution to the solution of the shared problem?
- What can a transdisciplinary approach look like in practice (methods, ways of working)?

5.2. Session 2: Housing affordability and affordable housing provision (3.9.21)

The session on “Housing Affordability and Affordable Housing Provision” explores conceptual as well as empirical information. The first part of the session explores the concept of housing affordability from the consumer point of view: what factors affect it and how can it be measured to identify ‘sustainable’ access to living in housing. In the second part of the session, examples of the provision of affordable housing and trends therein from different European countries are presented and discussed.

Learning aims:

- To introduce ESRs to the concepts and mechanisms of housing affordability and affordable housing.
- To develop ESRs’ knowledge to evaluate mechanisms of affordability policies and practices and different contexts.

Learning outcomes:

- Identify and explain different concepts and measurements of affordability in housing and different approaches/mechanisms of affordable housing provision.
- Critically reflect on the relative merits of each concept and approach.
- Apply the above knowledge to design alternative concepts of housing affordability measurement and alternative approaches to deliver affordable housing.

Table 3 shows the programme of Session 2.

Table 1. RMT1 Session 2 programme (3 hours)

When?	Duration (minutes)	Programme	Who?
14:00-14:10	10'	Introduction of the program	Adriana/Marietta/ Gerard
14:10-14:35	25'	Presentation housing affordability exploration	Marietta
14:35-15:10	35'	Group exercise I: Discussion on 'improved' measurement of affordability; ins and outs of different concepts	All, led by Marietta
15:10-15:30	20'		Break
15:30-15:55	25'	Presentation/discussion on affordable and sustainable housing provision: international examples of policies and practices.	Gerard
15:55-16:30	35'	Group exercise II: Discussion on examples of affordable and sustainable housing delivery in the home country of participants and alternative, more effective, approaches. What makes a practice effective?	All, led by Gerard
16:30-17:00	30'	Evaluation / next session	Adriana/Marietta/ Gerard

5.3. Sessions 3a,b: Housing sustainability (17.9 and 8.10.21)

There were two sessions dedicated to discussing the meanings of sustainability and related terms, and their implication in housing design and building: 1. An introduction to the key concepts of concerning sustainability: meaning and evolution of the term; dimensions and pillars; perspectives and systems; goals and indicators. 2. Implications for housing design and building: whole building design approaches, industrial vs. sustainable design aesthetics; integration of architectural and urban scales.

Learning aims:

- To introduce key notions of sustainability, and their implications for affordable and sustainable housing
- To understand the correspondences between the systemic nature of sustainability in the whole building design approaches
- To grasp the interlinks between housing sustainability and affordability

Learning outcomes:

- A capacity to critically understand the systemic nature of sustainability, its underlying principles and objectives
- A capacity to understand sustainability and affordability as indissociable approaches to contemporary housing provision

- A capacity to envision solutions for housing which encompass sustainable and affordable dimensions

Table 4 shows the programme of the two sessions on sustainability.

Table 2. RMT1 session 3a (17 September) and 3b (8 October) programme (4 hours)

Schedule	Topic	Participants
Sept. 17 14:00-14:45	Introduction to key sustainability concepts	Leandro Madrazo
Sept. 17 14:45-15:30	Group exercise followed by discussion	ESRs
Sept. 17 15:30-16:00	Discussion	All
Oct. 8 14:00-14:45	Lecture: Sustainable (and affordable) housing	Leandro Madrazo
Oct. 8 14:45-15:30	Group exercise followed by discussion	ESRs
Oct. 8 15:30-16:00	Discussion	Leandro Madrazo

5.4. Session 4: Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing (23.9.21) (Lisbon Workshop)

The field of housing research is characterized by siloed thinking with little debate across disciplines. The aim of this event is to consider the way in which housing is approached from different disciplinary perspectives and to think about ways in which transdisciplinarity can be improved across Europe and the UK.

An open roundtable on the topic “Transdisciplinarity Research for Affordable and Sustainable Housing” will be chaired by Flora Samuel, Professor at the University of Reading, UK.

Panel members will be:

- David Clapham, Professor of Housing and Urban Studies, University of Glasgow
- Gilles Debizet, Professor in Urban Planning, Université Grenoble Alpes
- Doina Petrescu, Professor of Architecture and Design Activism, University of Sheffield
- Ashraf Salama, Professor of Architecture, University of Strathclyde

Learning aims:

- To introduce ESRs to different approaches to transdisciplinary research on housing, and to approaches bridging research and practice
- To help ESRs reflect on the evolution of housing studies and on their possible contribution to the field

Learning outcomes:

- Identify and explain different disciplinary and epistemological approaches in housing studies
- Critically reflect on the way transdisciplinary research on housing answers specific research questions or research objectives
- Critically reflect on their own (trans)disciplinary approach in relation to the existing literature and to examples of transdisciplinary research practices

Table 5 shows the programme of Session 4, and Figure 2 is a screenshot of the roundtable participants

Table 3. Session 4 Lisbon Workshop roundtable programme (3.5 hours)

When?	Programme	Who?
9:00 – 9:40 (CET-1)	Meeting online with Flora Samuel to prepare for the debate	Flora Samuel
10:00 – 11:15 (CET -1)	Public Online Debate	Flora Samuel and the roundtable participants
11:45 – 12:30 (CET -1)	Panel session with the ESRs. Discussion based on questions from ESRs relating to their own research projects.	All, led by Flora Samuel

Figure 1. The roundtable participants of the 4th session of RMT1

5.5. Session 5: Vocabulary workshop (15.10.21)

Based on the group work initiated at the beginning of the course (Session 1) the ESRs will identify and define (with reference to the literature) key terms that they will be using in their projects. The ESRs will submit three relevant terms in advance of the session and will be clustered into groups of two or three to work on defining one of these terms during the session. The definitions will be presented to the group for review and discussion. The definitions will be refined and presented as a RE-DWELL vocabulary entry to be submitted after the workshop (independent work Task 1, see also Section 5.6).

Learning aims:

- To introduce ESRs to the key terminology of housing.
- To contribute to the RE-DWELL vocabulary for affordable and sustainable transdisciplinary research.

Learning outcomes:

- Have a knowledge of key housing terminology
- Critically reflect on the relative merits of definitions.
- Apply the above knowledge when developing own literature reviews and glossaries.

Table 6 shows the programme of Session 5.

Table 4. Session 5 (3 hours)

When?	Duration (minutes)	Programme	Who?
14:00-14:05	5'	Why is the REDWELL vocabulary so important?	Flora
14:05-14:20	15'	Introduction: Issues of definitions	Jean-Christophe
14:20-14:30	10'	Keywords and systematic literature review	Flora
14:30-15:30	30'	Small Group exercise I: Development of definitions of key terms	Groupwork
15.30-15.40	10'	BREAK	
15:40-16:50	70'	Presentation/discussion of definitions group by group	All
16:50-17:00	10'	Evaluation / Reflection on the session	All

5.6. Session 6-Mapping the (trans) disciplinarity of the ESR's research (17.11.21) (Nicosia Summer School)

The session "Mapping the (Trans) disciplinarity of the ESR's Research" took place during the Nicosia Summer School. In this session, ESRs will critically present the essay written by another peer as part of the Task 2. The five-minute presentations should focus on the integration of the topics of RMT1 ("transdisciplinarity", "affordability", "sustainability") in the research projects.

Each presentation will be followed by a discussion led by a staff member from the RE-DWELL network.

Based on these discussions, a collective mapping of the disciplinary approaches put forward by the different RE-DWELL research projects will be elaborated. This map will reflect the structure acquired by the network four months after the initial mapping exercise realized during the Introductory days, in July 2021.

Learning aims:

- To support the development of the ESR's individual research projects by consolidating their disciplinary and transdisciplinary theoretical and methodological standpoints.
- To map the evolution of the RE-DWELL network and its position in the field of housing studies

Learning outcomes:

- Analyse different research approaches to housing in terms of research aims, theoretical backgrounds and methods (interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, etc.)

- Analyse the research project of a peer and make recommendations for improvement.

Programme:

- Morning session 10:00 – 12:45 (CET+1)
- Afternoon session 14:15 – 16:30 (CET+1)

5.7. Independent ESR work

Independent ESR work was set up to provide flexibility in order to help the ESRs with research activities for their dissertation. ESRs were to do three tasks that had been introduced in earlier RMT1 sessions, while the tasks involved homework, which was followed up with a discussion (in groups) and/or peer review during later sessions of the course. Task 2 and Task 3 are related, while Task 1 provided material for collecting project-relevant definitions.

The descriptions for the three tasks are as follows:

TASK 1. Group work: Vocabulary definitions of main concepts used in ESR projects

Each ESR will choose three key terms that are relevant for their research (Table 7). A list of key terms proposed by researchers of the RE-DWELL network will be provided in Session 1 to start thinking. The three chosen terms have to be communicated via the Group Work_RMT1 Channel in Teams before the next session, on September 3rd.

The ESRs will be clustered in groups of two or three to work collectively on definitions of the chosen terms that are meaningful for their own research projects. The definitions should take into account different disciplinary and theoretical approaches, and relate to the ESRs research questions and methodologies.

The definition of one of the terms chosen by each ESR will be discussed by the group in the “Vocabulary Workshop” (Session 5 on October 15th). The collective outputs of this task will be presented as vocabulary entries (500 words, plus references). Submission date: 22.10.2021.

TASK 2. Individual work: Essay

ESRs will be required to produce a 2,500 - 3,000 words essay revisiting their own research proposal, including their research questions, and integrating the different components of the RMT1 course (submission date: before 12.11.2021):

- Definitions of the key terms used in their research proposal.
- Critical synthesis of the existing literature on transdisciplinarity and presentation of their own standpoint in terms of disciplinary, inter- or transdisciplinary approach and methodology.

Table 7. RMT1 Session 6 ESR vocabulary choices. Colours except for green show overlap in topics for ESRs

ESR	TERM		
Annette	Industrialized construction	Life-Cycle Analysis	Circular Economy
Saskia	Neighbourhood (20-minute city)	Co-housing (or) Social Housing	Housing retrofit
Christophe	Housing governance	Housing stakeholders	Social housing
Aya	Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA)	Socioeconomic Impact	Codesign
Mahmoud	Social housing	Decarbonized housing	Sustainability tools
Marko	Social (rental) housing	Housing policy	Housing innovations
Anna	Housing tenure	Housing regime	Action-research
Andreas	Urban Governance (Co-governance)	Sustainable housing	Co-creation
Phren	Transgressive learning	Direct action	Co-creation
Zoe	Co-creation (community-based participatory research)	Co-housing	Housing renovation
Tijn	Housing policy/governance	Energy Poverty	Vulnerability
Alex	Housing policy	Uplift property premium	Energy efficiency within EU
Androniki	Urban Governance (Co-governance)	Participation	Transdisciplinary Research (or Community-based participatory research)
Leonardo	Housing regeneration	Participatory design (housing)	Social value

TASK 3. Individual work: Peer review of TASK-2 essay written by another ESR

A five-minute presentation should critically assess the disciplinary position of the research proposal of another ESR and make recommendations.

The peer-reviews will be presented during the Nicosia Summer School in November (Table 8). They will be further used as support for mapping the network of the ESRs' research projects based on their disciplinary standpoints and their possible developments (Figure 4).

Table 8. RMT1 Session 6 – TASK 3 peer review (10:00 – 12:45 (CET+1) and 14:15 – 16:30 (CET+1))

No.	ESR	Peer reviewer	Discussant (from beneficiary)
1	Tijn	Saskia	Adriana
2	Andreas	Aya	Joris (replaced by Adriana)
3	Saskia	Tijn	Carla
4	Anna	Marko	Joris (replaced by Adriana)
5	Marko	Anna	Adriana
6	Zoe	Phren	Marietta
7	Leonardo	Christophe	Gerard
8	Mahmoud	Annette	Nadia
9	Christophe	Leonardo	Flora
10	Phren	Zoe	Andreas
11	Annette	Mahmoud	Flora and Gerard
12	Androniki	Alex	Carla
13	Alex	Androniki	Adrienne
14	Aya	Andreas	Flora

6. Resources

Learning was facilitated by the resources (mostly literature suggestions) that all session organizers and coordinators suggested. They also asked ESRs to prepare the sessions by reading the literature selectively, keeping their dissertation in mind. Also, the literature and other resources offered opportunity to continue reading for the three RMT1 tasks (Section 5). They were provided via MS Teams folders.

The folder structure was the following:

- Course description
- Sessions (1-2 pager descriptions per session)
- Resources
- Tasks
- Recorded lectures

7. Outputs

As described in Section 5, ESRs were to do three tasks which led to the following outputs:

- Task 1 – Individual and group work: ESRs presented their definitions in writing and orally in Session 5 Vocabulary Workshop on 15.10.2021. After review, these will be published on the RE-DWELL on line vocabulary.

- Task 2 – Individual work: ESRs were required to produce a 2,500 - 3,000 words essay revisiting their own research proposal, including their research questions, integrating the different components of the RMT1 course. Submission date: before 12.11.2021
- Task 3 – Individual work: ESRs were required to peer review the essay written by one other ESRs for Task 2 and give recommendations. This took place during the Summer School (SS1) in Nicosia, on 17 November 2021. Figure 4 summarizes the resulting collective map of ESRs' (trans)disciplinarity research.

Figure 2. RMT1 Session 6 collective map of the ESRs' research using Miro. Source: Adriana Diaconu, UGA

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the RMT1 course in three contexts: in the Workshop in Lisbon, the roundtable followed by discussion; in the Summer School in Nicosia, the peer-review of ESRs' essays and the evaluation of the course as a whole. The highlights of each evaluation are presented next; Annex 1-Evaluation survey contains the full evaluation results.

Workshop 1 (Lisbon):

As presented in Deliverable 3.1, the online survey for the RMT1 day was completed by 13 ESRs and 4 supervisors/co-supervisors, resulting in a response rate of 63%, showing the following results:

Question	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Please evaluate [RMT1] Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	17	4.6	3.9	4.3

In Deliverable 3.1 (pp. 13-14) it is reported that the roundtable session was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“The content was of high quality and I think it brought some of the most interesting discussions of the workshop. The hybrid setup was effective for what it was (though of course in person would have been even better)”.

“Well organised, pertinent speakers, good background readings”.

“Fascinating topics, helped to better understand the concept of transdisciplinarity”.

Nevertheless, some ESRs commented that they did not have enough time to discuss with the guests, and the hybrid session was not considered as ideal for debate:

“(…) It would have been good to have more time to ask questions and interact with the members of the panel”.

“All in all, I think the format was the right one and I expect to see more of this kind of events, even with longer debates”.

“The only thing that I would mention is that the speakers introduced new concepts which are very helpful for interdisciplinary research and most of us were not familiar with this vocabulary. This is why it would be useful to have dedicated more time to the speakers to have 30 min presentations before the discussion so that the topics would be introduced more clear and holistically to us. I think more time was needed for such important and concentrated topics”.

Summer School 1 (Nicosia):

Sixteen participants partly evaluated the Summer School through an anonymous online survey. For the RM1 day (peer review), the 15 available responses averaged to 4.5 out of 5 points for the most positive evaluation:

Question	Answers	Average
Please evaluate Research Methodologies and Tools session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4.5

Some of the positive feedback referred to:

- *“understand the position of all of the ESRs and to know more about their own research”*
- *get “in-depth feedback” and specified “other ESR and supervisors feedback”*
- *“also hear everyone else's peer review ... Very useful and relevant”*

A positive summary comment was stated as follows:

“Both the ESR’s peer-review presentations and the discussions were of high quality and have helped create links within the network and improve ESR’s research. The learning aims of the session have been met.”

The negative comments related to not having received more detailed guidelines about the purpose and the content of the exercises and about getting acquainted with specific research methods. One ESR doubted the learning of the task: *“All in all, I’m not sure I learned how to do a peer-review after this session”*, while another found that *“some peer review of other ESRs sounds aggressive and I did not like that”*.

Overall course evaluation:

RMT1 was evaluated by 11 ESRs through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending and participating in the various activities of RMT1 and to identify areas needing improvements to inform the development of RMT2 and RMT3. Annex 1 contains the full survey and responses, while the Likert scale responses turned out as follows:

Questions (rating from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	Answers	Average
How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the RMT1 course? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4.3
Session 1 (Online seminar, July 16)	12	4.0
Session 2 (Online seminar, September 3)	12	3.8
Session 3a (Online seminar, September 17)	12	3.6
Session 3b (Online seminar, October 8)	12	3.6
Session 4 (Lisbon roundtable, September 23)	12	4.3
Session 5 (Online seminar, October 15)	12	4.1
Session 6 (Nicosia Summer School, November 17)	12	4.5
You are expected to demonstrate understanding of different approaches to transdisciplinarity.	12	3.3
You are expected to demonstrate understanding of different disciplinary perspectives to housing research.	12	3.5
You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse and position your own research and that of another ESR within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines.	12	3.7
You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse different research approaches (methods, methodology).	12	3.1
You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse the use of two fundamental concepts of housing studies.	12	3.7
You are expected to demonstrate ability to create a transdisciplinary research proposal in which you defend an own approach to transdisciplinarity based on the critical synthesis of the course mat...	12	3.5

On average the learning objectives scored lower than the sessions while the overall score for the course amounted to a 4.3 which is higher than for most other items, except for Session 6 (4.5) and Session 4 (4.3). ESRs express that the content and usefulness of most sessions was

generally high (above 4.0, except for Sessions 2 and 3), while the learning objectives were satisfactorily achieved.

Some positive feedback included:

“Overall, it was a satisfactory series of seminars that cover the fundamental aspects of research methods. Sessions planned, assignments and deadlines were delivered, therefore, I consider it was a successful module”.

“I believe we have a good starting point in understanding affordability and sustainability concepts in analysing them with respect to housing studies”.

“The organisation was very good and the modes of teaching the sessions were engaging for the ESRs”.

“It helped by providing me with the motivation and the path to start writing”.

“The writing assignments allowed me to reflect on crucial aspects of my research project. Likewise, the group activities and discussions about the key concepts that govern our project are better internalised and interlinked between ESR”.

“The round table in Lisbon was very interesting, as well as the Nicosia summer school exercise. Both of these were very relevant and quite substantial in terms of input and interaction”.

This feedback confirms the highest ratings for the Workshop 1 and Summer School 1 sessions in comparison to the other ratings, which coincide exactly with the ratings given in the Workshop 1 and Summer School 1 evaluation (summarized in the beginning of the paragraph).

ESRs suggested the following:

“It was well structured, but all the side assignments took up substantial time from our own research work. The essays are a great way to work on terms and definitions related to the ITN and our individual projects, and the Miro sessions worked great”.

“Relevant within the project, not really relevant in terms of methods”

“Group work is helpful to understand how colleagues think”.

“Very relevant although not sure why it was called RMT, maybe should be called Definitions lessons”.

“It felt very vague and general, which might be understandable in a setting-the-tone way, but I would like to know more about actual research methods in the future. The literature is so vast and chaotic and it would be great to have someone to help us navigate it and find our own position within the different approaches and methods”.

“Actual research examples, I know the organizers of the course produce great research. We need to know how they use these methods, run us through their research projects”.

“I would like to see more interactive sessions, based on Miro, less ‘homework’ and something more creative than the traditional lecture model”.

“Similar tasks are welcome, and the more related to our work the better to make the most of our time on this project”.

“I would love that some of the professors participating in this project share with us their research workflow. From how they organize their references and folders till publishing a paper. That would be a great help.”

The feedback shows a mix of reactions ranging from ‘useful course for the phase of study ESRs were in’ to ‘too little emphasis on methods and tools’, also by supervisors in relation to their own research. ESRs also commented that there should be less homework and more interaction. It was important for them to start getting familiar with the key concepts of RE-DWELL and relating them to their own research.

The following conclusions for future courses can be drawn from the responses:

- More interactive sessions, as well as time for questions, linked to shorter lecture time.
- More guidance on techniques for the preparation of the fieldwork and understanding the academic literature will be the core of RMT2, for example by supervisors explaining their uses of methods.
- Better link between learning activities and learning objectives/outcomes.
- Clearer instructions that learning should be as much as possible linked to own project of the ESRs.
- More generally, better expectation management (in relation to the proposal).
- Involvement of ESRs in design of courses.

Annex 1 – Evaluation survey

This annex contains the questions and answers to the evaluation survey.

Please evaluate the organization, content and learning outcomes of the RMT1 course, and their impact on your Career Development Plan. The purpose of this evaluation is to know what worked well and what needs to be changed in the next edition of the courses.

1. COURSE ORGANIZATION

How would you rate the overall organization of the blending of RMT1 online sessions with Workshop (Lisbon) and Summer School (Nicosia) activities of the RMT1 course? (from 1 to 5)

On a scale of 1 to 5, the majority of responses are '4' with four '5' (average is 4.3)

Comments:

- It was well organised.
- It was well structured, but all the side assignments were consuming substantial time from our own research work. The essays are a great way to work on terms and definitions related to the ITN and our individual projects, and the Miro sessions worked great.
- In general well organized and clear. Maybe some unclarities regarding certain things but overall very good.
- Online sessions worked well, no specific remarks.
- Overall, it was a satisfactory series of seminars that cover the fundamental aspects of research methods. Sessions planned, assignments and deadlines were delivered, therefore, I consider it was a successful module.
- Good use of Teams, Miro, breakout rooms etc.
- The organisation was very good and the modes of teaching the sessions were engaging for the ESRs.
- Good balance between both.
- Very well organised.
- In general, well organised and timely communication. Sometimes tasks not clear, such as how deeply to conduct review of another ESRs paper (in the end it resulted in most of us having different criteria and rigor). Another example would be RMT essay (task 2) as it was not the clearest what exactly to do, course description was different than what was provided during online session.

Do you have any suggestion to improve the organization of the future RMT courses in terms of blending of learning and types of teaching and engagement methods?

Comments:

- It worked.
- I would like to see more interactive sessions, based on Miro, less "homework" and something more creative than the traditional lecture model.
- Perhaps more action-oriented learning types rather than theoretical ones.
- As our research projects will continue progressing and data collection and analysis will come to the fore, I would like to suggest the inclusion of modules about different software that can be useful for our projects. For instance, Nvivo for qualitative research and Stata for quantitative research.
- Well delivered and good seminars.
- The different types were very engaging.

- To limit the lecture duration to 30-45 min and increase the use of interactive platforms.
- No.
- No suggestions.
- Clearer explanation of tasks.

2. COURSE CONTENT

How would you evaluate the following sessions (from 1 to 5)

Session 1 (Online seminar, July 16) Introduction to RMT1 course / Introduction to transdisciplinarity

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are six '4', three '3' and '5' each (average is 4.0)

Comments:

- Don't really remember.
- The presentation helped to foster understanding of transdisciplinarity.
- Important first steps for the network. An opportunity to familiarize us with the work environment and the themes that will steer the project.
- Good introduction and the timeline was well explained.
- Nice introduction to the course.
- It was more confusing than helpful
- Very relevant although not sure why it was called RMT, maybe should be called Definitions lessons.
- Very interesting speakers and well explained what is ahead of us. Gave us good introduction to the course and transdisciplinarity. Group work is helpful to understand how colleagues think.

Session 2 (Online seminar, September 3) Housing affordability and affordable housing provision

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are six '4', two '2', one '3' and three '5' each (average is 3.8)

Comments:

- Probably the only session that had methods content. However, it was clearly geared towards a non-expert audience.
- I would have liked a bit more actionable knowledge about indicators of housing affordability. Discussion was interesting.
- Rich in content and interesting examples of what is happening in other countries in Europe.
- Good seminar and very informative on the side of policy and finance, I would like more of these.
- Very useful context of the presentation as well as very relevant to RE-DWELL.
- Ok
- The content was limited
- Not many new concepts introduced and could be more useful if made more challenging.

Session 3a (Online seminar, September 17) Housing sustainability – Part 1 Key terms and definitions

In the scale 1 to 5, there are two '2', four '3', three '4' and three '5' (average is 3.6)

Comments:

- Definitions are not research methods.

- Most information was very basic, I think for all ESRs.
- A good conversation starter for our shared glossary. Definitions are a major issue in which all of us should get involved and carefully consider, even more in the midst of a collaborative research endeavour.
- Very useful in getting a better understanding of sustainability.
- Very useful session in the context of understanding definitions. Not only for sustainability, but for extrapolating the discussion (e.g. on diagrams and visualisation) in other terms too.
- Interesting and gave us a wide range of knowledge on sustainability. The presentation was so good and well-organized.
- Very relevant. More content in the form of academic papers would help.
- Interesting and useful team work, good critique of visualisation and graphic design, made us question what is usually used for demonstrating sustainable development and other "overburdened" words.

Session 3b (Online seminar, October 8) Housing sustainability – Part 2 Sustainable and (affordable) housing

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are six '3', five '4' and one '5' (average is 3.6)

Comments:

- No methods
- The interactive part in which all ESRs presented cases, concepts and visualisations was engaging, as was the lecture about sustainable and affordable housing.
- Relevant when considering the context of our project. However, it felt a bit disconnected from part 1, perhaps the scope was a tad broad. The group exercises were very interesting.
- Would be better to go into more depth on the difference between social and affordable housing and how these terms are different in various countries, as this provides the backdrop to all of our projects.
- Very useful context of the presentation as well as very relevant to RE-DWELL.
- It would have been great if the concepts had been introduced from the perspective of research methods.
- Encouraged us on critical thinking. I liked it.
- Same as above: Very relevant. More content in the form of academic papers would help.

Session 4 (Lisbon roundtable, September 23) Cases of (trans)disciplinary housing research

In the scale 1 to 5, there are two '3', five '4' and five '5' (average is 4.3)

Comments:

- Theory but no methods, also just one interpretation of transdisciplinary.
- Speakers were great.
- Very refreshing and insightful.
- Very useful to hear about case studies and get a better understanding of transdisciplinarity. Though I think this term is still quite elusive and not concretely explained. Perhaps it would be useful to go over the connector task definitions of transdisciplinarity produced by the ESRs to get a better universal understanding, and from different angles (pedagogy, community participation, sustainability, affordability etc.).
- Very engaging for everyone and high level of presentation by most of the panel.
- Time for questions was not adequate.
- ESRs did not have time to ask enough questions.

- Discussion team could be more transdisciplinary.
- Very good choice of speakers and interesting discussion, especially after the public part finished.

Session 5 (Online seminar, October 15) Vocabulary workshop

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are six '5', two '2', one '3' and three '4' (average is 4.1)

Comments:

- Vocabulary is not a method.
- I would have liked more time for discussion. Time management in general could have been better.
- It was relevant and useful for our research. The explanation about the assignments and deliverables was a bit unclear.
- Very good task, worked well with the fellow ESR and very much enjoyed the process which was enriching and also further forged links between our work.
- Very useful session and very well delivered.
- The best part of the whole course! It was interesting and useful to understand the importance of identifying my research key terms from the start. Besides, it simplified the idea of definitions.
- Most relevant as we are at the stage of dealing with definitions and fit well with ESRs timing.
- Interesting speakers and topic on how to define certain values.

Session 6 (Nicosia Summer School, November 17) Mapping the (trans)disciplinarity of the ESR's research

On a scale of 1 to 5, there is a majority (seven) of '5', one '3' and three '4' (average of 4.5 is highest of any session)

Comments:

- Relevant within the project, not really relevant in terms of methods.
- The peer review session was absolutely amazing. I would like more of this.
- The peer review activity was quite challenging and stimulating. The roundtable was very engaging and relevant at the current stage of the project.
- Again great session forging links and it provided an opportunity to express concerns and doubts which we could try to give our opinions on to resolve between ourselves.
- Very creative and engaging exercise.
- Very good to understand the topics of each other. I would prefer to have received a guideline on how to conduct a peer review.
- Same as above: Most relevant as we are at the stage of dealing with definitions and fit well with ESRs timing

Please explain which sessions best met your expectations and why.

- The session on housing affordability had methodological content, the others had no methods or very thin explanations, for example, what is a variable or what is a correlation.
- The round table in Lisbon was very interesting, as well as the Nicosia summer school exercise. Both of these were very relevant and quite substantial in terms of input and interaction.
- I thought the session on affordability and the one in Lisbon were the most interesting in terms of content!
- Session 6, the peer review session, was exactly what I would expect from this programme. Researchers from other disciplines actively engaging with each other's work.

- The Nicosia summer school. It was a very engaging, fruitful, and well-organised event.
- Nicosia session, and the tasks were well thought out and beneficial.
- The session 5 on vocabulary was very useful for me, as it related to research methods.
- Vocabulary workshop. The best part of the whole course! It was interesting and useful to understand the importance of identifying my research key terms from the start. Besides, it simplified the idea of definitions.
- Vocabulary workshop: Most relevant as we are at the stage of dealing with definitions and fit well with ESRs timing.
- Perhaps exercise with mapping transdisciplinarity felt a bit ad hoc but it was interesting to visualise other ESRs in the circle and understand how we are/are not connected by interests.

Please explain in which ways has the RMT1 course contributed to the development of your research?

- The essay has pushed me to write and start working on a paper.

It helped in providing me with the motivation and the path to start writing.

- I think they allowed to build a common understanding of these key terms between all of us.
- Especially the interactive sessions genuinely helped. The lectures less than I hoped.
- The writing assignments allowed me to reflect on crucial aspects of my research project. Likewise, the group activities and discussions about the key concepts that govern our project are better internalised and interlinked between ESRs.
- The vocabulary tasks have been extremely useful and related to my individual work. It has also helped to forged new connections with ESRs which have led to other fruitful conversations about our projects and the potential to write a joint paper.
- Understanding the concepts of affordability, sustainability and transdisciplinarity and trying to find my own stance in disciplinary terms.
- The definitions and key terms identification.
- It was new and extremely beneficial for me that I as a researcher is the one to identify how I am using a certain term in my research and to identify its context.
- Helped in focusing on definitions and learning how others ESRs deal with this.

Please provide any suggestions on the content of the future courses on Research Methods and Tools (TMT2 & RMT3). For information, RMT2 is about *Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis*; RMT3 is about *Transferring research findings to community stakeholders* (according to research proposal).

- Actual methods not vagueness about concepts. The issue is that one method fits all approach clearly doesn't work. To be relevant for individual research projects and input, you need to create streams of methodological training for example, a quantitative stream that runs through the basics of regressions, clusters and their implementation. On the other hand, a qualitative stream that does evaluate design by really going into detail about survey design. Otherwise, the training remains to superficial so everyone can understand it and it doesn't really tackle real issues. We need to find a scientific frontier in our fields and produce knowledge there, hands on training on methods are an integral part of this.
- It felt very vague and general, which might be understandable in a setting-the-tone way, but I would like to know more about actual research methods in the future. The literature is so vast and chaotic and it would be great to have someone to help us navigate it and find our own position within the different approaches and methods.
- Definitely more peer reviews and I would like more specific methods. Most of us are going to do interviews, so it makes sense to cover the different techniques rather than basic knowledge about sustainability.

- The inclusion of modules about different software that can be useful for our projects. For instance, Nvivo for qualitative research and Stata for quantitative research.
- Similar tasks are welcome, and the more related to our work the better to make the most of our time on this project.
- It would be great if the next course on Research Methods and Tools actually provided knowledge on different Research Methods and Tools for conducting research. Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed methods, tools for researching, tools for organising our work. This mapping of different techniques would give a great boost on our understanding of academic research.
- To build on the existing outcomes.
- To provide clear instructions for some specific tasks (I am referring to the peer review task, where it seems each ESR interpreted the task from their point of view, and everyone forgot the primary purpose of the task - where I believe it was to encourage reflections on the existing scientific discussion around the transdisciplinary. some of the feedbacks were purely linguistics and have entirely missed the purpose of the session).
- I would love that some of the professors participating in this project share with us their research workflow. From how they organize their references and folders till publishing a paper. That would be a great help.
- Could be named something else.
- Perhaps introductions to broad words could be shorter and some challenging real life examples could be introduced.

3. LEARNING OUTCOMES

For each of the aims for learning outcomes of the RMT1 course, please indicate to what extent you think you have achieved it (from 1-not achieved at all to 5-fully achieved).

- You are expected to demonstrate understanding of different approaches to transdisciplinarity.

On a scale 1 to 5, the majority (seven) are '3', one '2' and four '4' (average is 3.3)

Comments:

- Excluding my own approach, i do not understand others.
- I get the impression that transdisciplinarity is interpreted only in one specific way, through the "beyond academia" lens, while it can be so much more. I am in the process of forming my own definition so in this sense, the course gave me a good start and significant food for thought.
- The readings were helpful, although not all of great quality.
- I'm in the process of fully engaging with this concept and applying it to my project.
- I have written about the meaning of transdisciplinarity from a couple of perspectives but it would be better to understand it from more angles and for this to be discussed as a group so that we are all of the same understanding, such as from an affordability perspective.
- In order to understand different approaches it would have been great if we analysed them in relation to the research methods each is using. The 'research methods' part was missing from this course.
- It is still quite ambiguous to explicitly identify a number of certain approaches.
- Transdisciplinarity in itself was not the main focus of discussions.
- Before, the term was very vague, but after this course, it became clear what is transdisciplinarity, how complex it is and what are other classification with respect to transdisciplinarity, such as multi- or inter- disciplinarity.

- You are expected to demonstrate understanding of different disciplinary perspectives to housing research.

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are three '2', two '3', five '4' and two '5' (average is 3.5)

Comments:

- Beyond social sciences and economics, I did not get anything clear.
- I certainly cannot claim to fully understand how economists or social scientists perceive and approach housing research. Maybe this has to do with how much focus has been given to architecture, since most of the ESRs are architects.
- I would say 'sustainability' or 'affordability' are not disciplines. The affordability session was most insightful in this regard, explaining how housing could be 'home' in anthropology and 'assets' in economics.
- Currently, I am exploring this aspect through my literature review.
- I have been made aware in multi- inter- trans- disciplinary research which is helpful in understanding my own project and how I will approach it, and the benefits to different approaches.
- Similar to the above.
- I understood how each discipline perspective is different approaching housing research.
- Not enough time to engage in the depth of disciplinary knowledge.
- Still relatively new to the subject and will take a bit more research and interaction to fully understand how other disciplines affect parts of housing research

- You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse and position your own research and that of another ESR within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines.

On a scale of 1 to 5, the majority (nine) scored '4'; there are one '2' and two '3' (average is 3.7)

Comments:

- I think most ESRs do not understand what their disciplinary standing is.
- Thanks to the peer review!
- This aspect was very well addressed in the written assignments for both RMT1 and TS1.
- I have a better understanding of this following the peer review, where I better understood other ESR's opinions on transdisciplinarity and their proposed approaches for their projects.
- The assignment and peer review was a very useful exercise on this regard.
- Yes.
- Difficult to do still.
- Interactions and poster work were a bit limiting as we only worked with a couple of our peers, it could be somehow made that we gather around a couple of words of the highest interest for us in a couple of rounds, making sure we all met other ESRs with the same interests and keywords.

You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse different research approaches (methods, methodology) to housing issues in terms of discipline (monodisciplinary, interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity)

On a scale of 1 to 5, there is one 1, three '2', three '3', four '4' and one '5' (average is 3.1)

Comments:

- Very little methods content.
- Again, it has been quite vague, but maybe it's because this is an introductory course.

- Almost nothing on specific methods up to now.
- I'm in the process of fully engaging with these concepts and applying them to my project. However, I have progressed in the definition of my research approach in terms of theory and methodology through the assignments of the module.
- See 24.
- It would be very useful to have an exercise that relates methods to disciplines. Then we would have been able to solidly compare between different cases. Still we are doing this process through own experience and not through a taught knowledge.
- Kind of.
- Research methodologies were not that much a part of this.
- Still a bit of practice will be needed as we haven't been introduced to methodology and tools that would help us analyse methodological approaches.

- You are expected to demonstrate ability to analyse the use of two fundamental concepts of housing studies - affordability and sustainability - and apply them in your own research work.

On a scale of 1 to 5, there are two '2', two '3', six '4' and two '5' (average is 3.7)

Comments:

- A concept is not a method.
- In terms of conceptualisation the sessions were nice. Not so much on operationalisation.
- I have addressed both separately. The next step is to combine them through a comprehensive analysis of case studies.
- Well understood and written about in the RMT1 essay.
- This part felt disconnected from the idea of research methods. It is however understandable that the concepts are very significant for RE-DWELL. Again correlating them with methods would have made more sense.
- Yes I was able to further relate both to my research.
- To an extent yes.
- I believe we have a good starting point in understanding affordability and sustainability concepts in analysing them with respect to housing studies.

-You are expected to demonstrate ability to create a transdisciplinary research proposal in which you defend an own approach to transdisciplinarity based on the critical synthesis of the course mat...

In the scale 1 to 5, there are five '3' and '4' each, and one '2' and '5' each (average is 3.5)

Comments:

- The approach I have to my own project was barely covered.
- The last essay helped in this.
- My research proposal has been refined as the project is evolving. The next steps are well envisaged and planned with my research team of supervisors and secondments.
- This is understood, though the project may ultimately not be transdisciplinary due to the nature of the secondments, case study, project brief etc. Therefore it may not be a choice as to whether the project is transdisciplinary, however I have gained a good understanding of how it could be and what the term means.
- The focus given on different transdisciplinary approaches was very helpful. Constructing our own stance was also approached through the assignment. However this is still a very challenging matter as we didn't discuss enough about tools in each discipline.

- With further investigation, yes I can.
- Not enough course materials, but the presentations began to build on the subject.
- I believe with the understanding of transdisciplinarity, we are well equipped to find a proper methodology in research proposal.

4. CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN

What aspects of the RMT1 course could be enhanced to support the objectives listed in your Career Development Plan?

- Actual methods training with hands-on experience. I need to get better at quantitative analysis, R coding.
- Actual research examples, I know the organizers of the course produce great research. We need to know how they use these methods, run us through their research projects.
- More in-depth knowledge, some of the presentations were too superficial.
- maybe essay assignments that we can use as material for future papers.
- I would prefer more operationalisation and less conceptualisation in the coming months, especially since the course is called 'methods and tools'. Experts in qualitative and quantitative methods could be invited as guest speaker. Perhaps we could peer review each other's preliminary method sections in the spring.
- As mentioned before, the inclusion training on certain tools to manage quantitative and qualitative data would be a valuable improvement. Also, the development of new channels for dissemination such as the podcast or YouTube channel can boost the impact of the project among an audience that goes beyond academia.
- Application by writing joint papers with fellow ESRs, this would be beneficial to my understanding of the RMT1 themes, to develop our projects, and to produce impactful work that is open access and promoted on the website and blog in addition to my personal social media channels.
- The course was very engaging in terms of lectures and content in discussing about transdisciplinarity, affordability and sustainability as concepts. As discussed already, one would expect that it would focus more on research methods, schools of thought or paradigms in order to advance ESRs' toolboxes with new knowledge useful for the construction of the research at these early stages.
- To present clear examples of a previous transdisciplinary research.
- Perhaps methodology selection and tools available for researchers. Nothing in depth at this point, but a poster overview of main clusters of methods and approaches could help us in visualising methodological approaches.